

Data-Driven Methodology for Energy Demand Monitoring and Anomaly Detection in Commercial Buildings

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Abstract. This study addresses the challenge of accurately monitoring and assessing energy usage in commercial buildings. In many buildings, anomaly detection due to faulty conditions of sensors, actuators, or controllers is reactive and requires significant time and effort. The proposed solution addresses the problem using pre-existing information, without necessitating additional resources. The methodology involves collecting and processing electricity demand data, segmenting it into weekly intervals, and identifying typical usage patterns through clustering. Representative clusters define a building's standard weekly demand profile, serving as a benchmark for monitoring and comparing demand patterns. To enhance the monitoring process, threshold-based alerting mechanisms ensure timely identification of significant deviations in usage patterns. If a significant deviation is detected, it is compared to the representative profiles of similar buildings. If these buildings exhibit the same deviation, it may indicate drastic changes in weather conditions, seasonality, or extremely high pricing, causing all customers to alter their behavioral patterns. In contrast, if the patterns of similar commercial buildings remain unchanged, this explicitly indicates problems within the specific building. Ultimately, our approach not only enhances the precision of demand monitoring, but also facilitates early anomaly detection, optimizing energy usage, and reducing operational costs to enhance the sustainability and efficiency of commercial buildings.

Keywords: Monitoring, Anomaly detection, Clustering, Energy demand profiling

1 Introduction

The European Green Deal is driving transformative changes in the building energy sector, emphasizing innovative, sustainable designs [3]. By focusing on building energy efficiency ratings, these designs aim to enhance energy performance and meet future demands, supporting environmental objectives and ensuring higher efficiency ratings.

Heating, ventilation, and air-conditioning (HVAC) systems, which account for up to 40% of energy consumption in commercial properties, are a key focus for reducing emissions. Innovations like smart services built on Building Energy Management Systems (BEMS) can automatically control operations, including HVAC, lighting, and equipment, leading to significant energy savings—18% for offices and 14% for retail stores [8].

Monitoring systems use energy demand data from smart meters to provide a broad, non-intrusive overview of energy use. Achieving energy efficiency in buildings is often challenging due to equipment failures and inappropriate operation strategies. Detecting anomalies in building energy consumption is crucial for enhancing energy savings. Effective systems require accurate and interpretable data analysis and anomaly detection, highlighting deviations from typical consumption patterns [1], [2]. Abnormal behavior can lead to higher power consumption, longer operating times, and potential device malfunctions. Promoting energy awareness and optimizing appliance operation can prevent energy waste [4], [5].

Anomaly detection methods using machine learning techniques can be divided into supervised and unsupervised learning. Supervised learning uses labeled data and includes techniques like decision trees [12], linear regression, SVM [7], and ANN [13], often employing residual analysis for anomaly detection. However, this can be inaccurate if residuals are small or influential factors are not considered. Unsupervised learning, which does not require labeled data, discovers structural knowledge and is more suitable for building managers. Typical algorithms include clustering and association rules, used to identify energy consumption patterns [11]. While unsupervised learning is better for real-world applications, it may be less effective than supervised learning due to the lack of prior knowledge and reduced efficiency in big data processing [4].

This study introduces an anomaly detection technique based on distance methods, utilizing specialized distance metrics to compare time-series subsequences. This approach identifies deviations from typical usage profiles, constructed through clustering to group similar weekly demand patterns. These clusters effectively represent the building’s usual electricity usage behavior, enabling the detection of anomalies that deviate from these patterns. The study encompasses 13 shopping malls, 16 office buildings, and 3 schools, providing a diverse set of usage profiles for analysis.

2 Problem statement

Anomaly detection and monitoring in time-series data involves identifying various types of anomalies that can occur in energy demand profiles.

2.1 Anomaly Detection and Monitoring

A time-series is defined as an ordered set $D = D_1, \dots, D_m$ of m real-valued, possibly multidimensional data points, each measuring electricity demand and related variables. A time-series anomaly is a subsequence $D_{i,j}$ that deviates from frequent patterns in D .

Anomalies are typically categorized into sequential patterns (deviations across contiguous points) and single-point outliers (individual points that deviate significantly).

For example, a consistent evening surge in demand indicates a sequential anomaly, while a sudden spike at a specific hour is a single-point outlier.

Various detection methods exist, including forecasting (comparing predicted vs. actual values), reconstruction (detecting large reconstruction errors of normal behavior), encoding (analyzing compressed representations), isolation trees (partitioning samples to find outliers), and distance methods (assessing deviations based on specialized metrics) [9].

This study focuses on distance methods, which integrate well with clustering algorithms and excel at detecting anomalies in high-dimensional data like electricity demand. They operate without labels (supporting unsupervised detection), handle large datasets efficiently, and facilitate real-time identification of irregularities, such as unexpected consumption spikes or drops.

3 Methodology

The proposed method for anomaly detection in building electricity demand data involves a structured, multi-step approach to ensure accurate and reliable identification of anomalies.

3.1 Overview of Proposed Framework

The process begins with data collection from electricity meters installed in buildings (Step I in Fig. 1). Once the data is collected, it undergoes preprocessing to clean and prepare it for analysis (Step II). This step includes handling missing values, normalizing the data, and defining relevant features that will be used in subsequent analysis. The goal here is to ensure the data is in a suitable format for analysis, improving the accuracy and reliability of the anomaly detection process. The objective at this stage is to gather comprehensive and accurate data that reflects the electrical usage patterns of the buildings. In the next stage, building profiles are created, and the centroid of the Typical Electricity Load Patterns (TELPs) is identified [10]. This involves clustering the data to find representative patterns of electricity demand for each building. The objective is to establish a baseline of normal electricity consumption patterns against which current data can be compared (Step III). Finally, the anomaly detection step involves comparing the current demand data against the identified TELPs. Deviations from these typical patterns are flagged as anomalies, indicating potential issues such as equipment malfunctions or unusual consumption behaviors. The goal is to identify and address deviations from normal electricity usage patterns, enhancing energy efficiency, and preventing potential issues (Step IV).

3.2 Energy Demand Profiling

To build the electricity demand profile, we first create weekly profiles for each building using the approach outlined below.

Clustering for standard profiles

Fig. 1: Main steps of the algorithm.

Data preparation and processing: To start, we select a continuous period of electricity demand data. The duration should be long enough to capture typical usage patterns while avoiding anomalies from shorter time frames. The data must be clean, addressing any missing values or outliers appropriately. This might involve using imputation techniques for missing data and filtering out extreme values that don't reflect normal operation. Special events or holidays should be excluded unless such variations are typical for the building during those periods.

Process of segmentation into weekly intervals: Next, we split the data into weekly segments. Each week provides a snapshot of the building's electricity demand pattern, capturing variations across different days. This segmentation allows us to observe recurring patterns and deviations characteristic of weekly cycles. When analyzing electricity demand data, it is crucial to ensure that the selected period converges to a specific profile that accurately reflects typical usage patterns. As illustrated in Fig. 2, the scaled profiles (up to 100%) for office buildings, schools, and shopping malls can be compared to identify these typical usage patterns.

Fig. 2: Typical electricity demand profile for different building types (scaled)

However, there are instances where the chosen period may not provide a clear profile. In such cases, alternative segmentation approaches and subset analysis can be employed to uncover more distinct patterns and insights. Breaking the data down into daily segments provides a more granular analysis. This can be particularly useful for identifying daily usage patterns, peak demand times, and any anomalies that occur on specific days. Separating the data into weekdays and weekends can reveal differences in electricity demand based on the building's operational schedule. Isolating data for periods with special events or holidays can help understand their specific impact on electricity demand. This information can be useful for future planning, allowing for better anticipation of demand spikes or drops during similar events.

Creation of representative clusters: To determine the representative profile, we use the k-Means clustering algorithm to define weekly profiles for each cluster. The k-Means approach focuses on minimizing the total variance by using the mean values as the centroids of the clusters Eq. (1).

$$\mu_j = \frac{1}{|C_j|} \sum_{P_{w_i} \in C_j} P_{w_i}, \quad (1)$$

where

μ_j is the centroid of the cluster j .

C_j is the set of weekly electricity profiles assigned to cluster j .

$|C_j|$ is the number of weekly profiles in the cluster.

P_{w_i} represents each weekly electricity profile in cluster j .

After clustering, we find the representative profile by calculating the median of all profiles within each cluster. A more detailed description of this calculation can be found in [6]. This method is less sensitive to outliers, providing a more robust representation of typical demand patterns while smoothing out short-term fluctuations (see Fig. 3).

Fig. 3: Profile of the building, indexed with hourly resolution. Light blue lines represent weekly segments and dark blue dashed line represents the centroid.

Additionally, by focusing on the median, this method ensures that the representative profile minimizes the impact of extreme values, leading to a more accurate and reliable depiction of the building's electricity usage.

Representative clusters establish a baseline for normal behavior, while the threshold-based alarm mechanism continuously monitors current data against this baseline. By comparing the current week's profile P_{cmt} with the representative profiles \mathcal{P}_j using distance methods, we can effectively detect and respond to anomalies in electricity demand. The distance between these profiles quantifies deviations from typical behavior. If this distance exceeds a predefined threshold, it indicates a significant deviation, triggering an alarm to alert the system or operators for further investigation.

Explanation of alerting process. When comparing energy demand, point-by-point comparisons using Euclidean distance or Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) are common, but they don't account for value shifts or scaling. Methods like Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) or Mahalanobis distance offer their own benefits in handling these issues.

However, using the Pearson correlation coefficient (PCC) can be more effective, as it also handles noise. The PCC is straightforward to calculate and interpret, making it ideal for real-time monitoring. It provides a clear metric for assessing how closely the current data aligns with the expected pattern. The simplicity, efficiency, and ability to detect linear relationships of PCC makes it a preferred choice for many applications in energy profiling and anomaly detection.

PCC quantifies the linear relationship between two time series (profiles) of equal length. It measures how closely the two electricity usage profiles move together. The coefficient ranges from 1 to -1 , where 1 indicates perfect positive correlation (both series increase or decrease together), -1 indicates perfect negative correlation (one series increases while the other decreases), and 0 indicates no linear correlation.

The Pearson correlation coefficient is calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{PCC} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})(r_i - \bar{r})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (r_i - \bar{r})^2}}, \quad (2)$$

where: x_i and r_i are the individual data points of the two electricity demand profiles time series; \bar{x} and \bar{r} are the means of the profiles $P_{\text{cmt}} = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$ and $\mathcal{P} = \{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n\}$, respectively; and n is the number of data points in each profile.

For example, when comparing two identical electricity demand profiles that are only shifted or scaled in the value dimension, the correlation remains perfect. The Pearson coefficient remains high even when noise is added to the time series. However, any shifting along the time axis (misalignment of the time intervals) will significantly reduce the correlation coefficient. This is because the Pearson correlation is calculated based on point-by-point comparisons between the two profiles, meaning that misalignment, or any substantial deviation in the timing of the values, directly affects the correlation score.

4 Case studies and method validation

The effectiveness of the Pearson correlation coefficient in monitoring and anomaly detection can be illustrated through several case studies, which validate its application across different scenarios. The threshold value is chosen as 0.96. All values above this threshold are considered as normal behavior of the system. This can be observed in case studies for all types of buildings. If the value falls below this threshold, an alert notification should be sent. An interesting case is the behavior of an office during a state holiday.

Table 1: Cases

Case	School	Office	Shopping
Case 0	0.979	0.995	0.996
Case 1	0.461	0.98	0.997
Case 2	0.819	–	0.946
Case 3	0.741	–	0.936
Case 4	0.662	0.957	0.987
Case 5	0.957	0.994	0.999

Case 0: Typical day, as shown in Fig. 4a–4c and detailed in Table 1. The table shows that the PCC for all building types exceeds 0.97.

Case 1: On May 1st, a public holiday, the energy usage pattern in shopping malls remains largely unchanged, as these establishments continue their operations. In contrast, office buildings exhibit a scaled-down version of their typical energy consumption, maintaining a strong correlation with their usual pattern (Fig. 4g and PCC = 0.98) despite the reduced activity. Schools, however, present a textbook example of the impact of the holiday, with a clear deviation from their standard energy usage profile Fig. 4d with PCC < 0.5 , highlighting the distinct differences in energy demand across various types of buildings on such days.

Case 2: During an experiment that introduced specific anomalies, the energy usage pattern became distinctly evident in schools, where deviations were clearly observable, see Fig. 4e with PCC = 0.819. In shopping malls, these anomalies were only slightly noticeable, reflecting a minor impact on their overall energy consumption.

Case 3: On a subsequent day of the same experiment, the observations mirrored those previously recorded. The energy usage patterns in schools continued to display clear deviations with PCC < 0.75, while shopping malls exhibited only slight variations with values PCC < 0.95 (see Fig. 4h).

Case 4: A system malfunction led to noticeable deviations in energy usage patterns across different building types. In office buildings, the impact of the malfunction was clearly visible, while in schools, the deviations were even more pronounced, making the anomalies highly evident. At the exact time of the malfunction, the trend of energy usage changed its angle from the typical pattern, resulting in a PCC value of 0.662.

Conversely, shopping malls showed almost no change, with their energy consumption remaining largely unaffected by the system malfunction.

Case 5: A subsequent minor system malfunction revealed distinct variations in energy usage patterns. In shopping malls, the anomalies were undetectable, maintaining a consistent energy consumption profile. In schools, the deviations were noticeable for a few hours, indicating a temporary impact, see Fig. 4f and $PCC < 0.96$. Office buildings, however, showed no visible changes, with their energy usage remaining stable despite the malfunction.

Fig. 4: Examples of anomalies

General observations reveal that schools are highly sensitive to changes and anomalies, making them ideal for illustrating deviations in energy usage patterns. In contrast, shopping malls and office buildings, due to their larger size and greater inertia, exhibit less noticeable patterns and are more stable in their energy consumption profiles. These case studies collectively underscore the importance of considering building type and operational characteristics when analyzing energy usage patterns and detecting anomalies. Understanding the nuances of energy usage across different building types is crucial for effective energy management and anomaly detection.

5 Discussion and conclusions

When an anomaly is detected in a single building, it often indicates a malfunction of the equipment within that building. However, if similar issues arise simultaneously in multiple buildings of the same type, or even spread to different types of buildings,

this may signal a broader change in customer behavior. For instance, a sudden spike in electricity prices for a specific hour might prompt users to turn off all non-critical infrastructure equipment. In addition, widespread anomalies could indicate general problems within the network, such as those that might occur when the Baltic states disconnect their electricity network from BRELL ring (the Russian and Belarusian grids). These scenarios highlight the importance of monitoring and analyzing energy usage patterns to identify both localized equipment issues and broader systemic changes.

In conclusion, integrating Distance Methods, particularly those based on PCC, into our anomaly detection framework offers a robust and versatile approach. These methods provide a comprehensive toolkit for analyzing energy usage patterns across different building types.

Case studies show that schools are highly sensitive to changes and anomalies, making them ideal for illustrating deviations in energy usage. In contrast, shopping malls and office buildings exhibit more stable energy consumption profiles due to their larger size and greater inertia. This underscores the importance of considering building type and operational characteristics when detecting anomalies.

Distance Methods, which integrate seamlessly with clustering algorithms and perform effectively in high-dimensional data, enhance our ability to detect anomalies in energy usage. They are particularly suitable for unsupervised tasks, offering comprehensive anomaly detection capabilities and computational efficiency.

Overall, a PCC-based distance method provides a powerful framework for real-time monitoring, anomaly detection, and energy management. This enables us to gain valuable insights into the dynamics of energy consumption and improve the efficiency of energy usage in different building types.

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References

1. Chen, Z., O'Neill, Z., Wen, J., Pradhan, O., Yang, T., Lu, X., Lin, G., Miyata, S., Lee, S., Shen, C., Chiosa, R., Piscitelli, M.S., Capozzoli, A., Hengel, F., Kühner, A., Pritoni, M., Liu, W., Clauß, J., Chen, Y., Herr, T. (2023) A review of data-driven fault detection and diagnostics for building hvac systems. *Applied Energy* 339: 121030. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.APENERGY.2023.121030>

2. Chiosa, R., Piscitelli, M.S., Fan, C., Capozzoli, A. (2022) Towards a self-tuned data analytics-based process for an automatic context-aware detection and diagnosis of anomalies in building energy consumption timeseries. *Energy and Buildings* 270: 112302. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENBUILD.2022.112302>
3. European Commission: COM(2021) 802 - Directive. Energy performance of buildings (recast), (2021), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52021PC0802>, last accessed 2025/01/21
4. Himeur, Y., Ghanem, K., Alsalemi, A., Bensaali, F., Amira, A. (2021) Artificial intelligence based anomaly detection of energy consumption in buildings: A review, current trends and new perspectives. *Applied Energy* 287: 116601. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.APENERGY.2021.116601>
5. Lei, L., Wu, B., Fang, X., Chen, L., Wu, H., Liu, W. (2023) A dynamic anomaly detection method of building energy consumption based on data mining technology. *Energy* 263: 125575. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2022.125575>
6. Maimon, O., Rokach, L. (eds.) (2010) *Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery Handbook*. 2 edn. Springer, New York
7. Nichiforov, C., Alamaniotis, M. (2023) Learning matrix profile method for discord-based attribution of electricity consumption pattern behavior. *Cogent Engineering* 10. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311916.2023.2199518>
8. Perry, C.: ACEEE american council for an energy-efficient economy. Smart buildings: A deeper dive into market segment, (2017), <https://www.aceee.org/research-report/a1703>, last accessed 2025/01/21
9. Schmidl, S., Wenig, P., Papenbrock, T. (2022) Anomaly detection in time series: a comprehensive evaluation. *Proceedings of the VLDB Endowment* (9): 1779–1797. <https://doi.org/10.14778/3538598.3538602>
10. Vassiljeva, K., Matson, M., Belikov, J., Petlenkov, E. (2024) Profiling and schedule based forecast of electricity usage to improve energy performance of administrative buildings. In: 2024 IEEE International Conference on Engineering, Technology, and Innovation (ICE/ITMC), pp. 1–8, IEEE, 24–28 June, Funchal, Portugal. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICE/ITMC61926.2024.10794299>
11. Yan, K., Huang, J., Shen, W., Ji, Z. (2020) Unsupervised learning for fault detection and diagnosis of air handling units. *Energy and Buildings* 210: 109689. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENBUILD.2019.109689>
12. Yan, R., Ma, Z., Zhao, Y., Kokogiannakis, G. (2016) A decision tree based data-driven diagnostic strategy for air handling units. *Energy and Buildings* 133: 37–45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENBUILD.2016.09.039>
13. Zhang, L., Guo, J., Lin, P., Tiong, R.L. (2025) Detecting energy consumption anomalies with dynamic adaptive encoder-decoder deep learning networks. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 207: 114975. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RSER.2024.114975>